

Tomographic Reconstructions Of The Enigmatic Thylacocephalan Arthropod *Dollocaris ingens*

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Abstract

The Thylacocephala are an unusual, enigmatic group of arthropods. Current knowledge of their anatomy and origins is extremely limited, their study with traditional palaeontological techniques impossible as a result of their all-encompassing carapace. This dissertation details the study of a single species of thylacocephalan arthropod, *Dollocaris ingens*, using the novel technique of tomographic reconstruction. The study demonstrates that this is a powerful approach, which can entirely overcome the previous limitations on research into the Thylacocephala, and has – for the first time – made the study of the class' internal anatomy possible.

Several fossils of *Dollocaris ingens* were acquired, of which one had internal anatomy preserved. From this fossil a serial slice dataset was built using a CT scan, and an initial full reconstruction was created using the custom SPIERS tomographic software. The same specimen was then serially ground, resulting in a second, more detailed dataset, and higher resolution reconstruction of the cephalic region. Details of the internal anatomy revealed are reported herein: *Dollocaris ingens* has eight posterior segments, each with an associated gill, three cephalic predatory appendages, a large stomach in the cephalic region with two sizeable digestive glands, and a ciliated mouth tube.

This new information helps solve a number of long-running anatomical disputes concerning the class. The highly derived character of a number of these features, juxtaposed with a number of very primitive aspects, disallows simple explanation of the group's origins, yet a close relationship to primitive crustaceans can be postulated.

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1. Introduction

Dollocaris ingens sp is an enigmatic Jurassic fossil species, a member of the unusual class Thylacocephala [biological classification = domain, kingdom, phylum, class, order, family, genus, species, with increasing specificity]. This class belongs to the phylum Arthropoda, and has poorly understood origins and affinities [relationships to other arthropods]. The earliest member is thought to date from the lower Cambrian (Vannier *et al.* 2006), while their presence in Lower Silurian marine communities is well documented (Mikulic *et al.* 1985). The Thylacocephala survived through to the Upper Cretaceous (Schram *et al.* 1999, Lange & Schram 2002), but despite such a long history - and twenty-five years' research - significant uncertainty about even fundamental aspects of the thylacocephalan anatomy remains.

Since the suitably idiosyncratic erection of the group by three independent sets of researchers in the early '80s (Arduini *et al.* 1980, Secrétan & Riou 1983, Briggs & Rolfe 1983), arguments concerning their mode of life, anatomy and ostensible relationship with the subphylum Crustacea have raged. Fuelled by lack of information arising from the fossils' all-encompassing carapace, this debate will only be solved by the application of a novel approach which overcomes the limitations of their study. One such method is the use of tomographic reconstruction, a technique applied in this project to reconstruct the 3D internal anatomy of *Dollocaris ingens*, and thus elucidate the relationships and ambiguities of the class. The aims of the project are, therefore, to build knowledge of the thylacocephalan anatomy including the gills, appendages (their identity and attachment), stomach, cephalon and trunk, and to try and ascertain the affinities of the class.

This dissertation details the first information of the soft part anatomy of a thylacocephalan arthropod, and contains a short background, highlighting the previous research and unanswered questions, the method employed for this study, results and discussion of the consequent implications (organised into sections on each element of the anatomy), and conclusions.

2. Background

The class Thylacocephala is an enigmatic group of arthropods with worldwide distribution and a long history, but poorly understood anatomy, origins and affinities (Vannier *et al.* 2006). They possess a bivalved, laterally compressed, all-encompassing carapace (Rolfe 1985) with an anterior rostrum notch complex [rostrum being a projection of the carapace – see glossary] (Schram *et al.* 1990). In *Dollocaris ingens* - the fossil reconstructed in this project – hypertrophied eyes fill the optic notches (Secrétan 1983, Fröhlich *et al.* 1992), but in other species these can be stalked (Schram *et al.* 1999). Emerging from the mid-point of the carapace are raptorials: very long geniculate [bent abruptly] and sometimes chelate [ending with a pincer-like claw] appendages (Secrétan & Riou 1983). Some authors have suggested the presence of five cephalic appendages: two antennae (Lange *et al.* 2001), and three raptorials (Pinna *et al.* 1982, Arduini *et al.* 1980). The latter, it has also been suggested,

could originate behind the cephalon, in the trunk region (Secrétan 1985). The fossil's posterior has a series of styliform [slender and pointed] and filamentous appendages, reminiscent of pleopods [abdominal crustacean limbs adapted for swimming/carrying eggs]. These decrease in size posteriorly (Rolfe 1985). Figure One shows a specimen of *Dollocaris ingens* with these features labeled.

Figure One – A summary diagram showing the current known anatomy of a thylacocephalan arthropod. The species is Dollocaris ingens. Shown are the external features, with gills drawn on the carapace to demonstrate their form. Organism varies in size from 10 to 300mm. See also summary line drawing, Figure Six. Photograph courtesy of Dr Jean Vannier. Scale bar 1cm.

The number of segments has been debated – a minimum of eight exist (Secrétan 1985), but up to

14 have been reported in Australian specimens (Briggs & Rolfe 1983), and even 20 in early forms (Mikulic *et al.* 1985). Little is known of the internal anatomy; most species have eight pairs of well-

developed gills in the trunk region, showing a fan-like array with dorsal recurvature [curvature posteriorly near the top of the carapace] (Schram *et al.* 1999). A large stomach is found in the cephalic region (Alessandrello *et al.* 1991, Vannier *et al.* 2006).

It is apparent that fundamental knowledge of the internal thylacocephalan anatomy is lacking. This can be resolved, however, by applying techniques which palaeontologists use to see inside the carapace. One such approach is tomographic reconstruction (Vannier *et al.* 2006), which has proved successful in three-dimensionally preserved fossils from the Herefordshire Lagerstätte (Siveter *et al.* 2004, Sutton *et al.* 2005). This technique requires a fossil preserved in three dimensions with soft tissue, such as those of *Dollocaris ingens*, a thylacocephalan arthropod found in the La Voulte-sur-Rhône Lagerstätte in France (Fischer 2003). This preservation occurs in concretions, the result of an unusual mineral assemblage - apatite → calcite ± gypsum → pyrite ± chalcopyrite → galena (Wilby *et al.* 1996). The fossils are perfect for reconstructions using the method described by Sutton *et al.* (2001), delivering models that can provide the first full internal anatomy of a thylacocephalan arthropod. This could help solve long running-disputes concerning its affinities, anatomy and mode of life. First described over a century ago (Meek 1872, Van Straelen 1923), the taxon was formally erected in the 1980s and it has since been assumed it belongs to the sub-phylum Crustacea (Arduini *et al.* 1980, Secrétan & Riou 1983, Secrétan 1985, Alessandrello *et al.* 1991, Lange *et al.* 2001), yet this has never been proven. Numerous factors can be used to identify crustaceans, the most suitable for *Dollocaris ingens* being the head arrangement of two antennae and three other appendages as mouthparts (Brusca & Brusca 2003). If reconstructions show this arrangement the assumption of crustacean affinities are sound.

Several aspects of the anatomy remain hotly debated, the most notable dispute being between the 'Italian School' and most other thylacocephalan researchers. From poorly preserved fossils originating

Figure Two: A reconstruction of a benthic mode of life for the thylacocephala (Pinna *et al.* 1985)

in the Osteno deposits of Lombardy, Arduini *et al.* (1980) inferred cirripede [barnacles and related crustaceans] affinities when erecting the class Thylacocephala. This conjecture – based upon the misinterpretation of the stomach as a reproductive organ – led the authors to conclude the frontal lobed structure was not in fact an eye, but a 'cephalic sac' used to attach the organism to the substrate, and further conclude it led a sessile, filter-feeding life. Upon identification of the mistake the 'Italian school' conceded this may not be the case, but proposed a benthic [sea floor dwelling] mode of life (Alessandrello *et al.* 1991, Figure Two), maintaining the

'cephalic sac' hypothesis, despite identification of retinula cells [a cluster of sensory cells in an arthropod eye] in *Dollocaris ingens* specimens (Rolfe 1985, Fröhlich *et al.* 1992, Vannier pers. comm.).

A more detailed anatomy will allow better interpretation of both mode of life (although it must be noted this could differ with species, as the Thylacocephala present a wide range of forms). The underlying structures of the cephalon will resolve the 'eye' argument, as the 'cephalic sac' would be a highly modified antenna. Hence this project will be the first to demonstrate the internal anatomy of any thylacocephalan species, and should resolve numerous long-running disputes. The taxon has never previously been reconstructed, so all information beyond the details of carapace, raptorial, eyes and posterior appendages detailed above, and the basic position of the gills and stomach, will be original.

3. Method

In order to reconstruct a thylacocephalan arthropod a suitable specimen of *Dollocaris ingens* was acquired from Dr Jean Vannier (Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1). To build a tomographic reconstruction, closely spaced cross-sectional images are required. These can be obtained by two methods – CT scanning and serial grinding with digital photography. The former is non-destructive, and thus preferable, especially with rare fossils such as the Thylacocephala.

Hence the specimen was first scanned with a micro-CT scanner (a technique explained in Ketcham & Carlson (2001); Instrument - Phoenix v|tome|x 's', with X-ray source energy of 160 kV and 16 bit flat panel 512 x 512 pixel direct digital detector). This gave high resolution (~30 micron) serial sections, spaced at 30 microns, which allowed a 3D reconstruction to be developed using the custom SPIERS software. The full process is described in Sutton *et al.* 2001, the included project notebook, and the SPIERS user manual in the appendix. In brief, the data was loaded into the program, and a threshold image created (Figure Three).

Figure Three – The stages of reconstruction from a CT scan. The far left image shows a section across the fossil from the CT scan. The middle figure shows the threshold image for this – every pixel above a certain brightness is set as fossil, and everything below as matrix. The right-hand figure shows this threshold divided into different parts of the anatomy as masks. Fossil 2.5cm at greatest width.

The three segments in the dataset were then manually edited (Dan Carrivick worked on the very posterior quarter of the specimen, the author editing the front two segments and the remainder of the rear segment), ensuring an accurate representation of the fossil in the threshold image. Next the fossil was separated into different parts ('masks'), which were subsequently edited to fit the feature of interest in every dataset image. This was done for every distinct fossil structure, allowing them to be viewed in reconstructions [visualization of the fossil and its constituent parts in three dimensions as ray-traced isosurfaces – see glossary]. These allowed interpretations to be improved and masks amended, as the relationship between different features becomes clearer in three dimensions. This

process complete, the structures could be identified - different parts of the reconstruction were displayed or hidden to create, for the first time, a clear picture of how the organism fitted together.

The results were not sufficiently accurate to meet the aims of the project, however, with poorly defined gills, and (what were initially thought to be) anterior appendages displaying poor resolution at the bases - a limitation of the CT scanner. Cephalic appendages were expected to prove vital to confirming the affinities of *Dollocaris ingens*, so further reconstructions were required. To obtain greater detail, new datasets were collected by serial grinding, and more fossils were supplied by Dr Vannier in order to corroborate findings with a second specimen. The nodules containing these were split with a rock saw, using the thinnest possible blade possible to minimise fossil loss. This revealed two new specimens, which – before grinding – required further cuts (Figure Four). The original specimen was also prepared for grinding as a precaution: if the internal anatomy of the new fossils had not been preserved, serial grinding would provide greater detail than the CT scan alone. For each fossil two 13mm slices were ground. In the previously reconstructed specimen the cut between the two (second cut, Figure Four) was made at the base of the second pair of raptorial appendages, to avoid losing either cephalic features or the mouth. In all specimens the resulting datasets included the front half of the fossil (vital to ascertaining the affinities), terminating past the base of the raptorial appendages.

Figure Four – Fossil preparation for serial grinding. A maximum thickness of 13mm could be ground, so suitable sections had to be chosen, shown schematically here. After an initial cut to identify fossil material, the specimen had to be divided into sections. Each section was then sawn square to provide edges to help align the images during reconstruction. Nodules from 3 to 8cm in length.

The prepared squares were then set in dark blue resin (to hold the specimens and provide colour contrast with the rock), then mounted on a slide holder with an ungrindable ceramic rim, and screw-scale. This allowed the rim to be lowered a set distance, and a known thickness of fossil to be removed for each grind. For these datasets the distance was 40 microns, and six minutes' grinding

(conducted automatically on a thin-section grinding machine) was required to remove the desired thickness. Between grinding runs the six specimens were individually photographed using a microscope and digital camera (exposure 130ms, resolution 30 microns, 1280x1024 demosaic .bmp image) to build the serial dataset. Further detail in Sutton *et al.* (2001).

Once this had been obtained, it was clear that only in the previously reconstructed fossil had the internal anatomy been preserved (Figure Five). Hence, another reconstruction was created for this specimen, showing the cephalic region in greater detail than the CT reconstruction. To achieve this, the images had to be aligned by rotating, resizing and moving the digital photos, a process done by hand with SPIERS Align software (manual included in appendix, and method in notebook). The images were then cropped to size, and a reconstruction built as described for the CT model. As this is time consuming, only features that could resolve remaining uncertainties (mouth, stomach, ‘anterior appendages’) or show finer detail (stomach, pouches) were reconstructed.

Figure Five – Examples of slices from the three Dollocaris ingens specimens ground: the left photograph is of the CT specimen, and clearly has internal detail preserved – the raptorial appendages in the lower centre, gills on the top left and right, and body in the centre. The central picture is a three-dimensionally preserved specimen, which nevertheless has no internal anatomy preserved, instead being filled with large calcite crystals. The right hand picture is another specimen, this one heavily crushed, destroying any internal details. Images 3cm wide.

4. Results And Discussion

The results of this project provide the first insight into the internal anatomy of a thylacocephalan arthropod. They are presented as images of the reconstructions created over the course of this research project, but the interactive models themselves are included – with full instructions – in the appendix. This allows users to view the reconstructions in stereo 3D, manipulate them, remove different parts, and investigate the features in greater detail than is possible from still images. It is recommended they are viewed in conjunction with the dissertation. High resolution versions of each figure are also included in the appendix. The current known anatomical details of the Thylacocephala prior to this project, as described in the background, are limited, and are summarised in Figure Six.

Figure Six – The current knowledge of thylacocephalan anatomy described in the background, and labelled here on a diagram of Dollocaris ingens; namely an all-encompassing carapace, an anterior rostrum-notch complex, three pairs of raptorial and hypertrophied eyes. The posterior has a series of eight slender and pointed appendages reminiscent of pleopods. Gills are found in the trunk region, showing radial disposition and posterior recurvature of the dorsal tips. Diagram altered from Vannier et al. 2006.

The fossil used to create the reconstructions (Figure Seven) had half a centimetre missing from the posterior (remaining length ~7cm) and lacked some details at the anterior margin, including the eyes and a short length of carapace between. The specimen also displayed minor deformation, namely compression ventrodorsally creating an unusually elongated form resulting from compaction during lithification. Figure Eight shows the CT model (used for the images in the results except where noted otherwise) of the specimen in the same position as Figure Seven for orientation. The results section is subdivided. Each part covers a single aspect of the internal anatomy (which is shown schematically in Figure Nine for reference and as an introduction), and contains a full description and discussion. This is followed by a discussion of the implications of the findings.

Figure Seven – The fossil from which the reconstructions in this project were created. Labelled are the typical thylacocephalan features, and the imperfections. The anterior dorsal margin was crushed for most of the cephalic region, the fossil was compressed ventrodorsally, and the carapace was poorly preserved at the front. Everything protruding from the carapace – raptorial, posterior swimming limbs, eyes – was absent, but the internal anatomy was preserved in great detail. Photographs courtesy of Dr J. Vannier.

Figure Eight – The full reconstruction of this specimen of Dolloccaris ingens, with all external features labelled, built from a CT dataset of the fossil. The same features as Figure Seven are labelled, the different colours representing different structures, masked separately during the reconstruction. All of the figures in the results section are created using this model except where noted otherwise.

Figure Nine – A summary diagram of the internal anatomy of *Dollocaris ingens*, all features described in the results section. In the cephalic region the mouth and stomach are found, with digestive glands (the term 'pouches' is employed for this report) on either side of the widest portion of the stomach. The mouth is protected by a plate-like structure much like a labrum (a median, unpaired flap projecting posteriorly over the mouth [Brusca & Brusca 2003]). This region also houses the anterior-most gills, the bases and attachments of the raptorial appendages, the raptorial tips pressed into the ventral margin, and a portion of the body (only that preserved is shown above, and this is incomplete). The rear comprises eight sternites [plates on the ventral surface of the body] and gills. The gills are located between the body and carapace. Scale bar (top right) = 1cm.

4.1. Sternites

The posterior of *Dollocaris ingens* comprises a series of eight segments, each with a set of pleopod-like appendages in life. These have been lost in this specimen, and what remains – and can be seen in the reconstructions (Figure Ten) – are the eight imbricated basal plates (sternites) on the ventral surface of each segment (rear two masked by Dan Carrivick).

Figure Ten – A reconstruction showing the sternites in Dollocaris ingens. These were well preserved with a high CT density, so proved easy to differentiate in scans. It is clear there are eight (first included in the body mask), and further investigation of the models shows their imbricated nature. Dorsal view has gills and carapace removed. Body not preserved above the sternites. Scale bar 0.5cm, arrow pointing anteriorly (towards the eye and cephalic region).

Also notable, dorsal of these well-preserved plates, are areas of lower CT density associated with them in the CT scan (Figure Eleven). The body was not preserved here.

Figure Eleven – A cross-section of the fossil from the CT dataset showing a basal plate, carapace and gill tissue, in addition to two patches of lower CT-density. Each sternite has such a feature, although the preservation differs. The rings in the scan are an artifact of the CT process. Scale bar 0.5cm, looking posteriorly.

The number of posterior segments (and hence swimming appendages) has been reported as both eight and sixteen. This work proves the former is correct. Specimens which appear to possess 16 could be the result of post-mortem slippage of the left and right sets as postulated by Rolfe (1985). The darker relief material is likely to be muscle tissue associated with the appendages; in fossils from the La Voulte-sur-Rhône Lagerstätte this is phosphatized (preserved with apatite, in contradistinction to pyrite for most other tissues), and often shows a density gradient of phosphatization towards the centre (Wilby *et al.* 1996). There is a gradient in the CT-density of these dark features (reflecting, possibly, a phosphatization gradient in muscle tissue). The composition (and hence likely original tissue) is impossible to prove without chemical analysis as the X-ray attenuation (controlling factor of the CT density) results from many factors including local variations in the density and porosity of the material, not just the atomic number. The position of the sternites necessitates a body attached at the interior dorsal margin of the carapace, and then stretching down to the base of the carapace where the sternites are situated.

4.2. Body

The body (Figure Twelve) in this specimen is poorly preserved and not well resolved – particularly posteriorly – in the CT scan. However, a more complete impression of its structure anteriorly is achievable: a ventral cavity houses the raptorial appendages, and immediately behind these the body surface slopes down and segues into the sternites (Figure Thirteen). Posterior to this the poor preservation prevents further direct study. In the cephalic region the body wall is situated around the edge of the raptorial bases, before moving dorsally and widening into the area around the stomach, at which point it is lost in this specimen.

Figure Twelve – Reconstructions showing the position and nature of the body. Possible body wall is preserved outside the first set of raptorial bases (masked separately due to the poor preservation and uncertainty). It is highly likely that in life the body wall followed the carapace to its ventral margin, a ‘hollow’ in the ventral surface of the body housing the raptorial bases, at least one of which (the smallest) could be folded into the carapace in this area .

Scale bar 0.5cm, arrow pointing anteriorly. High resolution version of this diagram included in the appendix.

Poor preservation of the body makes interpretation difficult. The nature of the gills, however, elucidates the nature of the body at the rear (discussed in the gills section). Coupled with the superior anterior preservation this gives sufficient detail for a convincing morphology (Figure Thirteen).

Figure Thirteen – A schematic sketch showing the form of the body of Dollocaris ingens. The upper diagram is a cross-section lengthways through the centre of the fossil, while the lower is a view from above (dorsal). The anterior cross-section shows only the preserved body, hence its termination at the front, but the gills have allowed the posterior to be predicted. Of note is the geometry of the body when accommodating both the gills and the raptorial appendages. Scale bar (top left of each image) 0.5cm, arrow pointing anteriorly.

4.3. Gills

There is one pair of gills per sternite/posterior metamere [segments comprising the body], situated at the side of the body, dorsal to the sternites (Figure Fourteen). Owing to compression this specimen does not show the fan-like array or strong recurvature seen in other examples. The gills are angled, however. They attach laterally to the body wall, but are poorly preserved, so this attachment cannot be constrained as either dorsal or ventral. For much of the fossil's length they are pressed against the carapace, an effect exaggerated by the crushed dorsal anterior. There is definite gill tissue in the cephalic region (unexpected as gills are usually associated with the trunk-region), and here this is more dorsally situated than the gills above the sternites. Owing to poor preservation the possibility that some of the posterior gill masks could be metameres must be considered, but their distinctive gill-like appearance in the CT slices (Figure Eleven), and a distinct separation from the median zone, makes this unlikely.

Lateral View

Figure Fourteen – A diagram showing the gills in this specimen. The preservation is patchy, creating a very noisy dataset. It is recommended the gills are viewed with an interactive model (included), which makes their morphology somewhat clearer, especially in stereo 3D. Scale bar 0.5cm, arrow pointing anteriorly.

Arthropod gills, while diverse in form and morphology, are typically one branch of a biramous [two-branched] trunk appendage. This is undoubtedly not the case here, and the gills must attach to the body wall (i.e. be pleurobranchiate) due to their position under the carapace. However, it must be emphasised that it remains unclear whether this occurs dorsally or ventrally (Figure Fifteen). The body has to attach to both the interior dorsal margin of the carapace (at least anteriorly, as this is where the carapace is excreted) and the sternites, stretching the height of the fossil.

Figure Fifteen – A diagram showing a single gill picked out by hand. This clearly shows the gill is detached from the sternites (and hence not a biramous appendage), but the point of attachment (ventral or dorsal) is not clear. Dorsal recurvature is present. Scale bar 0.5cm, arrow pointing anteriorly.

This leaves a gap between the lateral body wall and carapace in which the gills sit – the branchial chamber (Figure Sixteen). The pleurobranch gill arrangement is rare and highly derived, only being known in some decapods [an order of Crustacea including lobsters, prawns, crayfish and crabs]. In the Decapoda the attachment is ventral, just above the limb base (Brusca & Brusca 2003). However, the Thylacocephala have a very different segmentation pattern [differentiation into segments] from the decapods, so – even if the groups are related – in the time necessary for these contrasting segmentation patterns to evolve, the gill attachments could change significantly. Therefore similarities between the groups cannot provide strong evidence for the attachment point in *Dollocaris ingens*. The fan-like array with dorsal recurvature in other specimens is also noteworthy, and is necessary to explain the presence of gills in the cephalic region if the attachment is ventral (and thus posterior to this region – Figure Seventeen). Clearly further work is needed to confirm the gill morphology.

Figure Sixteen – A diagram showing the pleurobranch gill arrangement. 2-10cm across depending on size of organism.

Figure Seventeen – A diagram showing the gill morphology (slope, separation and curvature exaggerated). Gills 1 – 5cm.

4.4. Raptorial

There are three pairs of raptorial appendages, of which only the bases are preserved. These are numbered one to three, from the most anterior in attachment to the most posterior. All attach in the ventral gape towards the anterior, in a ‘hollow’ in the body’s ventral surface. The most posterior pair (number three) attaches at posterior of the cephalon, while the most anterior pair (number one) attaches right at the front of the fossil, immediately below the stomach, level with the back of the eye. Number three, the largest of the three pairs (with chelae) attaches medially and posterior to the middle pair. These appendages exit the carapace at a high angle (almost perpendicular to the fossil’s length), and have structures at their robust basal attachment (Figure Eighteen, labelled “Possible ‘gnathobases’”).

Figure Eighteen – A diagram showing the base of the raptorial appendages in Dollocaris ingens. Also included are the stomach, ‘labrum’ and tips of the raptorial appendages (discussion later in the results). The change in colour in three results from the boundary between two sections of reconstruction. One is the smallest pair of raptorials, and three the biggest. Scale bar 0.5cm, arrow pointing anteriorly.

The middle pair (number two) exits the carapace at a lower angle, but is very similar in form to number three. The attachments are lateral and slightly anterior to those of number three, and the limbs are robust and well-preserved. The smallest pair (number one) proved harder to discern while masking (thus required more interpretation), as the appendages are pressed up against the body wall for most of their length. They are similar in form to two and three, but almost parallel to the long axis of the carapace (Figure Nineteen). Their attachments are less at the anterior of the fossil, in the cephalon, where most of the carapace is occupied by the stomach. They are almost horizontal, and only exit the carapace posteriorly to number three. The attachments are robust, probably due to poor preservation anteriorly. There are no appendages anterior to the raptorials, unless they are at the extreme anterior where the fossil is missing (unlikely considering the small amount of such material). If Thylacocephala had a crustacean headplan antennae would be expected, and it is also clear that no highly modified antenna is present disproving the ‘cephalic sac’ argument for the eye.

*Figure Nineteen – A diagram showing the base of the raptorial appendages in *Dollocaris ingens*. The state of preservation of the limbs is clear, with number one showing the patchiest preservation. The angle of the appendages is also apparent. Scale bar 0.5cm, arrow pointing anteriorly.*

The greatest difference in the appearance of these limbs results from their angle: numbers three and two exit the carapace almost perpendicular to the longitudinal axis, while number one is almost horizontal. This is probably because the organism died with numbers two and three leaving the carapace at a high angle, with the joint bent acutely so the forelimbs were pressed back into the ventral opening (much like an arm bending so the hand touches the shoulder). Number one, however, shows a lower angle, probably because the two were drawn back into the ventral gape, only exiting at the first hinge where they bent out of the carapace. The two larger pairs could probably not be drawn into the carapace in this manner owing to their size. There is little uncertainty that these are the raptorial bases, while previous work and other specimens show that the largest pair exits medially (Figure Twenty), making this a likely – and well supported – explanation.

*Figure Twenty – A close up of the raptorial appendages in another *Dollocaris ingens* specimen. The smallest raptorials (which could be withdrawn into the carapace) clearly exit outside the larger two pairs. Photograph courtesy of Dr Jean Vannier. Scale bar 1cm.*

From their form the raptorial clearly had a predatory role, and the position of the mouth – at the base of number three - would at first appear problematic when using these to place food in the mouth. The stomach and mouth position are well constrained, as are the limb bases, so there is little doubt these are appropriately positioned. The length of the raptorial, and the number of joints - especially in the largest (with at least three, and a chelate ending, implying they were the most important for catching prey) - would allow great flexibility, and the unusual position of the mouth would thus prove inconsequential when feeding. The probable preservation of the terminal spikes of the raptorial appendages, pressing into the ventral gape (described below) between the attachments of one and two, supports this. It is clear there are no hidden joints under carapace as some authors have speculated (Secrétan 1985).

4.5. Stomach

Dollocaris ingens – like many arthropods – has a posteriorly directed mouth (Figure Twenty-one). This is situated at base of raptorial pair three, dorsal of the possible ‘gnathobases’. The mouth is in the form of a ciliated [with a margin of hair-like projections] tube (Figure Twenty-two) which splits off from the stomach prior to its termination (Figure Twenty-three).

Figure Twenty-one – Details of the stomach and digestive system of Dollocaris ingens. The stomach has two pouches on either side attaching towards the anterior, and a well developed foregut. The mouth is situated by the base of raptorial pair three. Scale bar 0.5 cm, arrow pointing anteriorly.

Also present is a strong plate-like feature immediately ventral to the mouth and large foregut, similar in appearance to the labrum found in many marine arthropods. This is less well preserved posteriorly,

but stretches from the mouth to level with the attachment of the pouches. It widens beneath the foregut, protecting its base. The gut itself widens considerably anteriorly, bulging out from the foregut into the head, to the extent that it occupies most of the carapace (not well preserved in this region).

Figure Twenty-two – A diagram of a slice of Dollocaris ingens, with the mouth and stomach in greater detail, showing their unusual nature, most notably the ciliated feeding tube, splitting off from the stomach. Also visible is the cephalic gill material, raptorials, and some of the stomach contents. Looking posteriorly.

At its widest point the two stomach pouches are present. These are oblate features with a strong slope, the dorsal, posterior halves showing excellent preservation, while the ventral, anterior portions are less well preserved. They appear to attach to the stomach anteriorly. Further towards the extreme anterior the stomach expands further to occupy most of the cephalon, and it is impossible to follow further as preservation becomes very poor.

The essential u–turn of the gut and passage to the posterior (necessary to position the anus at the end of the body as seen in all arthropods) is missing, but is likely to be small compared to the portion of gut seen here. Such a large stomach is very unusual in an arthropod, especially situated in the head. Small details are missing owing to the lack of the very anterior morphology and u–turn. Even without these details, however, we have a clear picture of the digestive system. The ciliated mouth tube is very unusual: the mouth is usually continuous with the foregut in arthropods. A similar arrangement is seen, however, in derived crustaceans, particularly crayfish and other decapods. While such

creatures' digestive systems differ markedly from that of Thylacocephala, this does suggest the latter are highly derived.

Figure Twenty-three – A diagram showing a reconstruction of Dollocaris ingens from photographic data. This allows greater detail than the CT scan, and the base of raptorial three, mouth, stomach and pouches are far better resolved. The mouth tube is seen splitting off the stomach, which continues dorsally to this, and terminating by the possible 'gnathobases'. Also apparent is the large foregut and sudden expansion into the head. The gap represents the width of the sawblade used to cut the specimen. Scale bar 0.5cm, arrow pointing anteriorly.

Chambers off the stomach are common in crustaceans for storage, grinding and/or sorting of food, again, most notably in decapods, which have a complex foregut system (Brusca & Brusca 2003). Such a function is unlikely here – the entire stomach is filled with matrix that the organism ingested when it died, yet the pouches are crystalline calcite. This suggests no large connection exists between them as would be necessary for passing food for further digestion or any other similar role. It is more likely these are some kind of gland, such as a digestive caecum [outpocketing with single opening] to aid chemical digestion. This is usually done in the mid-gut, and is also common in Crustacea. The structures at the base of the raptorial are reminiscent of gnathobases – arthropods process food with their limb bases, and have rough structures to aid grinding here. This seems somewhat unlikely in this case, however, as these structures are on the lateral, not the medial side of the limb base, so grinding food between them would be impossible.

4.6. Raptorial Tips

The ventral gape has an area, bordered by raptorial pair one and the 'labrum', with a series of linear insertions pointing towards the base of the stomach, initially identified as possible anterior appendages. These taper dorsally and do not appear to be attached to the body, being supported entirely by the matrix. There is another set of such structures anterior to this, right at the front of the fossil (clear in the CT data, masked separately – Figure Twenty-four) where the preservation of all other features is very poor. While most are similar in orientation, they are not symmetrical in number or position, and vary considerably in form. This makes it very unlikely they are a feature of the cephalon - for example, antennae. In the high resolution photographic reconstruction (Figure Twenty-Five) their relationship to the body wall is clear – namely they are not attached, some are merely pressed into it - and one is clearly at a very different angle from the rest.

Figure Twenty-four – A diagram showing the tips of the raptorial appendages pushed into the ventral gape of this fossil, between the bases of the first raptorials, anterior to the second. Scale bar 0.5cm, arrow pointing anteriorly.

There are a large number of these structures, far more than would be expected if they were antennae, and they are not symmetrical as such appendages would be. It is clear they are not attached. This fossil is generally well preserved internally, especially at this point in the cephalon, and arthropod appendages have strong attachments, which are unlikely to detach. It is even more unlikely they would stay 'floating' in the matrix of the ventral gape if that occurred. Hence it is very probable they represent something pressed into the ventral margin, and in this case the tips of the raptorials are the most likely possibility (especially considering their assumed positions at death).

Figure Twenty-five – A diagram showing a reconstruction of *Dollocaris ingens* from photographic data. The body wall, which is clear in this dataset is masked on at the insertions of the raptorial tips, showing they clearly do not attach. Also visible, which is not clear from the CT data, is one such structure at a very different angle from the others. Several more faint such structures are shown in the original dataset right at the edge of the ventral margin. Scale bar 0.5cm, arrow pointing anteriorly

4.7. Further Discussion

One of the aims of this project was to try to identify the affinities of the Thylacocephala. Whilst no incontrovertible conclusions can be drawn, the findings add a great deal of information to the debate, as outlined below. It is clear that the group shares various features with derived crustaceans (most notably decapods). The Thylacocephala have – in common with the crustacean headplan – three large mouthparts. We would expect, however, two antennae anterior to these, and for the mouth to be at the base of the first pair of mouthparts (the mandibles). This is clearly not so in the Thylacocephala. It is conceivable, however, that the very large foregut has been extended and the mouth moved posteriorly, and – as in other crustaceans with hypertrophied eyes such as hyperiid amphipods - the antennae are heavily reduced (Rolfe 1985). However, *Dollocaris ingens* has the wrong segmentation pattern for a decapod, which all have ten posterior swimming appendages, five thoracic and five abdominal, with the crustacean head arrangement and three thoracic mouthparts (Brusca & Brusca 2003). The earliest known thylacocephalan arthropod dates from the Cambrian (Vannier *et al.* 2006), while the Decapoda are thought to originate in the Devonian (Schram *et al.* 1978), so it is possible the Thylacocephala are stem group decapods (i.e. they split off from the decapod line prior to the most primitive living member of the group - before the last common ancestor of the true decapods [Budd

2001]). If this were so, the time it would take to evolve a different segmentation pattern would also be sufficient to lose the antennae and move the mouth posteriorly.

However, even if the antennae were reduced vestigial appendages would be expected, which is not the case (the missing anterior section is unlikely to house these as it is so small). This suggests the possibility that the Thylacocephala split off from the Crustacea earlier – before the first true crustaceans (Figure twenty-six). If the Thylacocephala were such stem group crustaceans, the highly derived character of much of the thylacocephalan anatomy could evolve by the Jurassic, yet the group would still lack some typical crustacean features (antennae and differentiated trunk appendages). Hence the last common ancestor of both the Thylacocephala and Crustacea would not have possessed such features, and this could show us the order in which these aspects of the anatomy evolved. Such discoveries could prove significant. Hence this work cannot rule out crustacean affinities, yet it is clear that no simple relationship to the Crustacea is present.

Figure Twenty-six – A diagram showing the phylogeny of the arthropods. There are, using the traditional grouping, four subgroups – the chelicerates, trilobites, crustaceans and uniramians. The above phylogeny shows the Thylacocephala as stem group crustaceans, more closely related to these than any other group, yet lacking the characteristics that would make them true crustaceans, suggesting they split off this line before the crustaceans' last common ancestor.

Despite the fact this is the first work on the internal anatomy of a Thylacocephalan species, some comparisons to previous work (largely predictions therein) are possible. Much previous research has focused on fitting the class into the crustacean phylogeny (Arduini *et al.* 1980, Secrétan 1983,

Secrétan & Riou 1983, Secrétan 1985, Alessandrello *et al.* 1991, Lange *et al.* 2001), and it is clear this is not as simple as envisaged. The possibility of a stem-group relationship to the Crustacea has not previously been postulated. Of the internal anatomy, the stomach pouches (Secrétan 1985), number and basic morphology of the gills (Rolfe 1985), and cephalic position of stomach (Alessandrello *et al.* 1991) has been identified previously.

The work has also disproved the assumption of a crustacean head plan (Secrétan & Riou 1983), thoracic raptorial, and a perceived lack of gills corresponding to the rear sternites (Secrétan 1985). All other internal features, and *Dollocaris ingens*' construction is new information which has little comparative material in the literature.

5. Conclusions

The Thylacocephala are enigmatic and unusual arthropods. Previously only external anatomy was well known. This project has revealed that within the all-encompassing carapace the Thylacocephala have eight posterior segments. Each has a set of pleopod-like appendages, and pleurobranch gills, situated in a branchial chamber between the body and carapace. The three raptorial appendages, known from the external anatomy, attach at the anterior of the fossil in the cephalic region, accommodated by ventral gape and unusual body shape. The large stomach has two large pouches, and is found in the cephalon, with a mouth situated dorsal to the posteriormost raptorial attachment. There appear to be no antennae. The internal anatomy suggests numerous similarities with the Crustacea, including some very derived features, but no relationship to any extant group is apparent.

Knowledge of the thylacocephalan anatomy has been significantly increased by these reconstructions, and the discoveries contribute significantly to the long-running debates concerning the affinities and palaeobiology of the class. Despite such advances, however, further work is clearly required. The lack of internal anatomy in three other specimens obtained for the project compels the findings herein to be based on a single fossil. Hence the reconstruction of another specimen of *Dollocaris ingens* is necessary to confirm the findings of this study, which must be considered tentative. Furthermore, in order to confirm that the findings for *Dollocaris ingens* can be applied to other Thylacocephala, another species needs to be reconstructed, preferably one from a different time period. The most likely lagerstätte in which a suitable three-dimensionally preserved thylacocephalan arthropod could be found is Mazon Creek, Illinois, which has several reported specimens (Schram 1990). All other deposits where the class is found tend to contain two-dimensional fossils. Further anatomical work, coupled with cladistic analysis, is likely to give more conclusive answers to the affinities of the Thylacocephala. The project has proved that tomographic reconstructions are valid for thylacocephalan work. It has demonstrated that they are an excellent tool for solving problems where traditional techniques are powerless. There are limitations, however. The method is slow, and very labour-intensive, but - most importantly - relies to some degree on personal interpretation due to the masking process. This is especially true of datasets as complex as those used in this study which had in the region of 1500 slices (for the full CT reconstruction) and a complex internal anatomy. Additionally, serial grinding is ultimately destructive, but this project has confirmed that – in metalliferous lagerstätte at least – CT is an excellent method of data acquisition which results in no damage to the fossil. With a little further work it seems certain that tomographic reconstructions can – after almost thirty years of lively, compelling and spirited debate – solve the mysteries that currently shroud the Thylacocephala.

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8. Appendices

Glossary

Antennae - mobile sensory appendages arising below the eyes at the front of the head, of which two are always found at the front of a crustacean head.

Benthic – Sea or lake floor dwelling.

Biramous – consisting of two branches.

Branchial chamber – gap between the carapace and body housing gills.

Cephalon - the head, or anteriormost body unit.

Chelate - ending with a pincer-like claw.

Caecum – outpocketing of gut with a single opening.

Ciliated - With a margin of hair-like projections.

Decapoda - An order of Crustacea including lobsters, shrimp, prawns, crayfish and crabs.

Dorsal - towards the top of the carapace.

Geniculate - bent abruptly.

Gnathobase – An expanded, hardened appendage base used to process food items before ingestion.

Hypertrophied – enlargement resulting from an increase in the size of cells, not the number of constituent cells.

Imbricated – With regularly arranged, overlapping edges, as roof tiles or fish scales.

Isosurface - a surface that represents points of a constant value within a volume of space, in this case the surface of a fossil.

Labrum - A median, unpaired flap projecting posteriorly over the mouth.

Metamere/Somite - Homologous segments, lying in a longitudinal series, composing the body.

Phosphatised – preserved with Apatite ($\text{Ca}_5(\text{PO}_4)_3(\text{OH},\text{F},\text{Cl})$)

Pleopods - abdominal crustacean limbs adapted for swimming/carrying eggs.

Pleurobranchiate – gills attaching to the body wall, housed in a branchial chamber.

Retinula Cells - A cluster of sensory cells in an arthropod eye.

Raptorial – predatory appendages.

Ray-tracing – rendering algorithm where mathematically-modelled visualisations are produced by following rays from the viewpoint outward, rather than originating at the light sources.

Rostrum - projection of the carapace.

Sternite - Plates on the ventral surface of the body

Styliform - slender and pointed.

Ventral – towards the bottom of the carapace.

X-ray attenuation - the decrease in the number of photons in an X-ray beam due to interactions with the atoms of a material substance.

Instructions for CD

Insert CD into drive and open with windows explorer. In the root directory are PDF versions of the notebook, dissertation, and – for a more detailed background into previous work on the thylacocephala - a literature review. Also included is the table recording the photos taken and any problems for the grinding run, and the manuals for the SPIERS software giving a more detailed idea of how the software works. Notebook material includes the .spv files showing progress in the cephalic reconstruction, referred to in the notebook, while the folder Figures has the figures from the report in higher resolution. Finally, the reconstruction folders contain the models from this project.

Instructions for models

For most computers installation is not necessary. Open the required folder: CT for the full CT reconstruction or photo for the more detailed reconstruction of the cephalic region from serial grinding datasets. Then drag the .sp2 file (photo reconstruction.sp2/ct reconstruction.sp2) onto sv.exe. This should open SPIERSview and a show progress in loading. Due to a bug this often freezes. This does not mean the program has crashed, as this very rarely happens – the screen is just not updated with progress. After a wait of up to 2 minutes the reconstruction should load. If this does not work, installation is required, for which the installer file (SPIERSview.exe) is included. Double click on the file and follow the on screen instructions. There is currently a bug with the MAC code, which is being recompiled. Mac users are kindly requested to email Mark Sutton (m.sutton@imperial.ac.uk) for a current version of this software. When the model is loaded the left button can be used to drag the reconstruction, and the right to rotate it. Page up and page down zoom in and out. The '/' mutes the colours, to allow the model to be viewed in stereo 3D, which can be turned on using the tab button. Pressing the keys listed below turns the features on and off. '#' makes the model rotate automatically, while the left and right arrow keys adjust the model's angle in the X/Y plane.

Key For Reconstructions

CT Reconstruction:

- 1 = Base of raptorial pair one (smallest)
- 2 = Base of raptorial pair two (middle)
- 3 = Base of raptorial pair three (largest) & sternite 7
- 4,5,6,7,8,V = Sternites 2 - 6
- A & F = raptorial tips pressed into ventral margin
- B = body and sternites 1 & 8
- C = carapace
- G = gills
- P = stomach & pouches
- W = single, hand-picked gill
- Y = possible body wall
- Z = diagenetic artifact in ventral margin

Photo reconstruction:

- 3 = base of raptorial pair three
- A & Y = raptorial tips pressed into ventral margin
- B = body wall
- P = pouches and stomach
- M = mouth

Overview Of Internal Anatomy

A summary diagram of the internal anatomy of Dollocaris ingens. In the cephalic region the mouth and stomach are found, with digestive glands on either side of the widest portion of the stomach. The mouth is protected by a plate-like structure much like a labrum. This region also houses the anterior-most gills, the bases and attachments of the raptorial appendages, the raptorial tips pressed into the ventral margin, and a portion of the body (only that preserved is shown above, and this is incomplete). The rear comprises eight sternites and gills. The gills are located between the body and carapace. Scale bar (top right) = 1cm.

Overview Of External Anatomy

The external anatomy of a thylacocephalan arthropod labelled on a diagram of Dollocaris ingens; an all-encompassing carapace, an anterior rostrum-notch complex, three pairs of raptorial and hypertrophied eyes. The posterior has a series of eight slender and pointed appendages reminiscent of pleopods. Gills are found in the trunk region, showing radial disposition and posterior recurvature of the dorsal tips. Diagram altered from Vannier et al. 2006.